

A smart-sensing AI-driven platform for scalable, low-cost hydroponic units

D4.3 Report on validation of microgreens production in operational settings

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ACRONYMS LIST

CHSK	Crop Health Sensor Kit
NCK	Nutrient-content Kit
FW	Fresh Weight
DW	Dry Weight
Rel FW	Relative Fresh Weight
Rel DW	Relative Dry Weight
HT	Height
LED	Light Emitting Diode
PAR	Photosynthetically Active Radiation
RH	Relative Humidity
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The activity *Task 4.3 Validation of performance of low-cost hydroponic units in operational settings*, had as an objective - *To carry out pilot trials and provide feedback for the refinement and calibration of the GOhydro platform*. In order to fulfill this objective USAMV Cluj built 2 GOhydro platforms, identical, to be able to do experiments in parallel, both in semi-controlled conditions and in operational, uncontrolled conditions. The GOhydro platform was built considering the recommendations from *Deliverable 2.1 Multi-modal Sensor Kit Specifications and Requirements*. USAMV performed the experiment with the GOhydro platform in operational conditions, with 2 species: basil (2 varieties: Germaline Basilic Bio and Basil Grand Vert) and lettuce (3 varieties: Paris White, Little Gem and Lolla Rossa). The methodology used for the research was derived from the one described in the deliverable *D4.1 Trial protocols for microgreens production in hydroponic units*. The influence of the environmental conditions outside the microgreen's cultivation spaces can influence the development of microgreens and their outcomes. That is why the external environmental data were also analyzed, using for this purpose the data collected by "Meteo Romania". The growing conditions of the two species of microgreens (basil and lettuce) is specific to the conditions in the operational environment, being also influenced by the external environmental conditions, for example especially by cloudiness. Thus, environmental parameters were seen to fluctuate; for example, temperature was seen to oscillate by 3-7 °C, with atmospheric humidity oscillation of 8-15 %, and respectively a variable amount of light (of 135-1645 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). The irrigation water had a constant temperature of 19-21 °C, a pH of 6.8-7, an electrical conductivity between 1.4-1.5 mS, and respectively a quantity of 6.4-6.5 mg L^{-1} dissolved oxygen. By comparison with the Duncan test, we found that the best amount of Fresh Weight was provided by Basil, variety Germaline Basilic Bio, with 883.40 g/m^2 . Basil provides the highest amount of Dry Weight, with a distinctly significantly positive difference compared to the control (average). The same results after processing the data with the Duncan test were seen for the 2 varieties of basil regarding the highest Dry Weight results. Furthermore, the variability of the data recorded for total phenols was very high, with the statistical processing not highlighting results with a significant difference. We showed that lettuce contained 98-105 mg/kg , and basil 106-127 mg/kg total phenols. From the morphological analysis of plant development, both in basil and in lettuce, no disease attack was registered, due to the maintenance of the health of the water in the feed basin and a quantity of around 6.4-6.5 mg L^{-1} of dissolved oxygen. An exception is made in the case of lettuce, the Paris White variety, which registered until harvest grade 4 in the degree of attack. Due to the higher thermal oscillations than in the case of the experiment under controlled conditions, the degree of attack was slightly higher. This is due exclusively to this variety in which the seed had an inadequate quality for the production of hydroponic microgreens. The conclusions of the experiment, which require the optimization of production procedures with the GOhydro platform, are related to the type of substrate used, the density of the microgreens culture, the attack by pathogens and the seed germination procedure.

In Denmark, we varied two experimental factors (Seeding Density and Fertilization) for three species (Basil, Pea, and Coriander) of Microgreens to better understand ways to optimize production, as well as offer comparisons to the other methods of cultivation employed in previous Deliverables 1.2 and 4.2. In our experiments, we identified some key tradeoffs, such as the increase in Fresh Weight accumulation and the decrease in Dry Weight accumulation via fertilization. However, fertilization was also associated with increased Height and Leaf Area. Finally, we identified that there was a slight negative effect of fertilization on Microgreen Health. Overall, we have shown that, despite tradeoffs, it is likely that fertilization is a highly net-positive input for producing Microgreens. The primary auxiliary concern, identified in Deliverable 1.2, is controlling pH to ensure optimal nutrient uptake from the fertilization solution. Using the GOhydro sensor kit offers a key tool to allow this quantification to inform the user when they need to add in a pH buffer; having this sensor kit offers a large advantage compared to other methods, such as multi-daily tedious measurements by hand. Concerning our second experimental factor, Seeding Density, we identified that it was space efficient, but it did not produce 50% more biomass, even though it was sown with 50% more seed weight. There was therefore a slight inefficiency in output, but this was compensated for by increased space efficiency, as there were more Microgreens per square centimeter. If space is not limiting, we recommend a standard or lower seeding density; if space is limiting, we recommend a high seeding density. Overall, we have validated the previous

methodological observations seen in previous deliverables by producing high-quality healthy Microgreens in uncontrolled environments.

Overall, considering the two separate sets of results obtained from GOhydro's two different pilot sites in Denmark and Romania, we shown some crucial Microgreen production dynamics. Firstly, we have shown the operational capacity of the GOhydro sensor kit, as we were able to successfully send real-time data from our pilot sites back to Greece. Secondly, we have elaborated on some important considerations in uncontrolled operational environments that can generally approximate the growing conditions of the average targeted user of the GOhydro products. Finally, both Romanian and Danish pilot sites have identified the large amount of species-specific variation; therefore, the selection of Microgreens to grow is an important first step for optimizing and parameterizing the growth environment. Therefore, overall, we have identified key production tradeoffs and pathways for Microgreen production that can be used by a variety of actors. Given specific constraints or operational considerations, we have identified tradeoffs and optimal pathways to produce the highest quality Microgreens. This deliverable followed previous work in Deliverables 1.2 and 4.2; in this case, our results have validated the use of GOhydro findings in a variety of environments, demonstrating the potential to be effectively used by a wide variety of users in different contexts and scales.

1 INTRODUCTION

GOhydro aims at developing a cost-efficient smart-sensing ICT platform capable of monitoring hydroponically cultivated microgreens’ environmental parameters and nutrient content in order to optimize the cultivation process and allow the harvest of the best possible products in many hydroponic installations. GOhydro aspires to culminate in the production of a radical platform that will be a shifting paradigm of how AI-driven technological innovation can become an affordable, accessible-by-all and user-friendly tool applicable to all forms of urban farming.

The purpose of the research made within WP4 concerns pilot trials in low-cost hydroponic units with a specific focus on the influence the environmental factors have on the growth and development of microgreens under hydroponic conditions. The hydroponic technology is analyzed with the goal to highlight, under the conditions of the GOhydro platform, in what way different environmental and nutritional factors can influence the development of microgreens and can improve its production and quality.

WP4 activity has 2 main objectives:

To design the trial protocols for evaluating the GOhydro platform in realistic uncontrolled installations and in operational highly controlled settings;

To carry out pilot trials and provide feedback for the refinement and calibration of the GOhydro platform.

Timetable of task components of WP4 are as follows:

Table 1.1: Timetable of task components of WP4				
Task	Month	Partners’ role	Activities	Deliverables
T4.1 Experimentation methodology for high-value nutrient design	[M10-M15] [01.12.2021-31.05.2022]	USAMV (lead), with participation of UCPH, SCiO, and NCSR-D	In formulating protocols, a minimum two of the four microgreens identified (basil, lettuce, coriander and mint) will be selected per location for testing in low-cost hydroponics units in Greece, Denmark and Romania. The protocols will define the data collection and data format to be followed, so that datasets generated in each trial site are comparable and combinable into a single, common dataset.	D4.1 Trial protocols for microgreens production in hydroponic units (R, PU) [M15] A report detailing the methods, materials and hydroponic units to be used for the GOhydro trials both in controlled and operational settings.
T4.2 Experimentation in controlled realistic installations	[M13-M24] [01.03.2022-28.02.2023]	SCiO (lead), with participation of USAMV	The low-cost hydroponic units to be used will be capable of supporting the growth of approximately 80-100 plants per production cycle. The trials will take place in two sites, Greece and Romania, where each partner will test at least two crops to sample the different growing environments.	D4.2 Evaluation results from experiments in semi-controlled realistic installations (R, PU) [M21] A report presenting and analysing the results and insights gained from the pilots under controlled settings.

T4.3 Validation of performance of low-cost hydroponic units in operational settings	[M19-M24] [01.09.2022-28.02.2023]	USAMV (lead), with participation of UCPH, SCiO, and NCSR-D	Production trials on the two identified microgreens in low-cost hydroponic units, will be carried out in Greece, Denmark and Romania in operational environments. These include office and living spaces for everyday use; the production parameters are not controlled. Feedback from these trials will be used for the final validation of the analytics components of the GOhydro platform.	D4.3 Report on validation of microgreens production in operational settings (R, PU) [M24] A report presenting and analysing the results and insights gained from the pilots under operational settings.
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The purpose of this research is to analyze in detail certain elements relevant for the microgreens crop grown under hydroponic systems, such as (Moraru et al., 2022): air temperature, water temperature, humidity, pH, electrical conductivity, different nutrient solutions, and the influence of light regimes (quantity, quality and photoperiods). This will situate growth regimes to allow for the control of diseases and pests and achieve desired growth and production trajectories. The goal of all these determinations is to contribute to the development of knowledge concerning the challenges of microgreens crops in a controlled hydroponic environment which will push forward discussions and practice in this segment of research and industry.

The experiments in semi-controlled realistic installations presented in Deliverable 4.2 are set up based on previous research seen in:

- Task 1.1 Review on nutrient and production parameters and light requirements (UCPH, SCiO, USAMV) [M1-M6];
- Task 1.2 Evaluation of optimised growth environments in controlled experiments and on the selection of promising recipes (UCPH & SCiO) [M4-M12];
- Task 4.1 Experimentation methodology for high-value nutrient design (USAMV, UCPH, SCiO, NCSR-D) [M10-M15];
- Task 4.2 Experimentation in controlled realistic installations (SCiO & USAMV) [M13-M24];
- Task 4.3 Validation of performance of low-cost hydroponic units in operational settings.

Furthermore, the protocols of deliverable D4.1 Trial protocols for microgreens production in hydroponic units (R, PU) [M15], define the data collection procedures and data format organization to be followed, so that datasets generated in each trial site are comparable and combinable into a single, common dataset.

In order to meet the requirements of the project so that the datasets generated in each trial site are comparable and combinable into a single, common dataset, the following principles for the elaboration of the hydroponic microgreen production protocol were suggested:

- IN OPERATIONAL ENVIRONMENTS SETTINGS – monitoring, but not controlling, environmental conditions (which will be different in the three centers: Greece, Denmark and Romania).
- Use of identical GOhydro prototypes - for comparable data:
 - Each pilot site (Greece, Denmark and Romania) is responsible for setting up a hydroponic installation on its own by following the guidelines of deliverable D2.1;
 - GOhydro has provide identical sensor kits (Crop Health Sensor Kit – CHSK and Nutrient Content Kit - NCK from Task 2.4). By Month 18 (August 2022) three sensor kits has be integrated and sent to the partners’ sites for testing within the framework of WP4.
- It is also important to use the same type of substrate for seed germination and growth, and to use the same variety of our common species (basil) in the three partner sites.
- Common protocols have been set for data collection, data formatting, and collection intervals.
- Data collection has been done using at least 3 repetitions.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 USAMV EXPERIMENTAL DESCRIPTION

The GOhydro platform was built considering the recommendations of *Deliverable 2.1 Multi-modal Sensor Kit Specifications and Requirements [M3]* (Table 4.1).

USAMV Cluj built 2 GOhydro platforms, identical, to be able to do experiments in parallel, both in semi-controlled conditions and in operational environmental conditions. In this deliverable, the results obtained under operational environmental conditions will be presented.

The construction stages of the GOhydro platform are presented in figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Construction of GOhydro platforms at USAMV

The GOhydro hydroponic platforms from USAMV Cluj-Napoca were built between February and October 2022, and each have the following components, systemically grouped:

- Structure Hydroponic System Storeyed Microgreens with 3 Trays (SHSM3T);
- System for Irrigation and Recirculation in Hydroponic Storeyed Microgreens SHSM3T;
- System for lighting and automation in Hydroponic Storeyed Microgreens SHSM3T.

The technical characteristics of the systems included in the GOhydro hydroponic platform are presented in tables 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3

Table 2.1: Technical Data Sheet - Structure Hydroponic System Storeyed Microgreens with 3 Trays		
No	Structure - SHSM3T	Characteristics
1	Number of modules SHSM3T	2
2	Type of structure	Demountable
3	Type of assembly	Demountable
4	Thickness of the system structure (mm)	20
5	Hydroponic system length (mm)	~ 800
6	Width hydroponic system (mm)	~ 450
7	Hydroponic system height (mm)	~ 1400
8	No. of floors of culture/module	3
9	Height to first floor (mm)	400
10	Distance between floors (mm)	300
11	No. of culture trays/module	3

12	Culture tray length (mm)	~ 670
13	Culture tray width (mm)	~ 320
14	Culture tray height (mm)	~ 30

Table 2.2: Technical Data Sheet - System for Irrigation and Recirculation in Hydroponic Storeyed Microgreens SHSM₃T

No	System for Irrigation and Recirculation SHSM ₃ T	Characteristics
1	Number of modules SHSM ₃ T	2
2	Nutrient irrigation system	Drip 1 line
3	Type of structure	Demountable
4	Type of assembly	Demountable
5	Irrigation columns/module	3
6	Nutrient recirculation system	Modular
7	Recirculating columns nutrients/module	3
8	Nutrient recovery system	Modular
9	Nutrient recovery columns/module	3
10	Distributor recirculation system/module	1
11	Valves (repair/maintenance)/module	1
12	Irrigation pump and nutrient recirculation	1
13	Nutrient tank	1

Table 2.3: Technical Data Sheet - System for lighting and automation in Hydroponic Storeyed Microgreens SHSM₃T

No	System for lighting and automation SHEM ₃ T	Characteristics
1	Number of modules SHSM ₃ T	2
2	Type of structure	Demountable
3	Type of assembly	Demountable
4	Lighting lamps	6
5	LED tube bulbs - 6500K - 18W	12
6	Lighting lamps/module	3
7	LED bulbs 6500K - 18W/modul	6
8	Lighting control system/module	2
9	Lighting/floor control system	6
10	Nutrient aeration system	1
11	Nutrient aeration pump	1
12	Nutrient aeration pump control system	1
13	Irrigation/lighting automation	1
14	Automation control system/module	2

USAMV performed the test with the GOhydro platform in operational environmental conditions, with 2 species: basil and lettuce.

The experimental conditions were:

1. For the basil:

Tray size (3): 64 cm x 31 cm = 1984 cm²

On each tray 2 varieties = 992 cm²:

- ✓ *Germaline Basilic Bio (Italiano classico)* = 3.84 g/tray (992 cm²)
- ✓ *Basil Grand Vert* = 3.78 g/tray (992 cm²)

Sowing date: 4/11/2022, 48 hours in the dark for germination

Substrate - hemp

2. For the lettuce:

Tray size (3): 64 cm x 31 cm = 1984 cm²

On each tray 3 varieties = 661 cm²:

- ✓ Paris White = 4.18 g/tray (661 cm²)
- ✓ Little Gem = 3.87 g/tray (661 cm²)
- ✓ Lolla Rossa = 3.98 g/tray (661 cm²)

Sowing date: 5/12/2022, 48 hours in the dark for germination

Substrate – hemp

The following devices were used for the measurements: Laserliner 082.130A LuxTest-Master Illumination Meter; wtw pH 315i - Digital pH Meter; Milwaukee Pro Portable Meters.

Drinking water used for irrigation has the following characteristics: pH=6.81, EC=261 µS/cm, TDS=389 ppm, Nitrites NO₂ = 0 mg/l, Nitrates NO₃ = 0 mg/l, Hardness = 14 °d

Also in environmental operational conditions, an experiment was carried out regarding - Influence of the substrate type on the production of microgreens, in the operational environment:

Substrate type:

Jute: Pro Micro Jute Microgreens Grow Mats by Handy Pantry - 10x20 Inches for 1020 Growing Trays - Pack of 10 Pads - Hydroponic Grow Media for Micro Greens & Wheatgrass Pro Micro Jute Microgreens Grow Mats by Handy Pantry - 10x20 Inches for 1020 Growing Trays - Pack of 10 Pads - Hydroponic Grow Media for Micro Greens & Wheatgrass: <https://www.amazon.com/Micro-Jute-Microgreens-Handy-Pantry/dp/B07T8KJB3>

Pads: Micro-Mat Minis Hydroponic Grow Pads - for Organic Production - Plant & Seed Germination: Wheatgrass, Microgreens, More - Measures 4" x 4" to fit 5" x 5" Greenhouse Plant Trays (48): <https://www.amazon.com/Micro-Mat-Minis-Hydroponic-Grow-Pads/dp/B00Y5TIJBO>

Felt: Biostrate - Felt Hydroponic Growing Pads; Biostrate felt microgreens grow pads are available in standard 10"x20" tray sizes, and in 120-foot x 9-inch rolls for hydroponic grow systems: <https://www.trueleafmarket.com/products/biostrate-felt-hydroponic-growing-pads>

Hemp: pressed local hemp / hemp bag.

2.2 UCPH EXPERIMENTAL DESCRIPTION

The uncontrolled experiments conducted at the Danish pilot site took place inside a greenhouse located at the Taastrup campus, University of Copenhagen, Denmark. This greenhouse had climate monitoring, but only actively controlled temperature with a set point around 20 degrees Celsius. The relative humidity was monitored but was not actively controlled. This allowed for natural fluctuations of air temperature and humidity that would also be present in other uncontrolled environments. Incidentally, as the temperature was around 20, the relative humidity was correspondingly lowered. This allowed us to approximate office or home conditions, with the specific average values seen in section 2.2.3. To achieve the stated objectives of Task 4.3, in Denmark we used a very simple setup that had only automation of the lights and temperature, which is a realistic controlled parameter in most homes or offices. Beyond that, for our central structure, we only used a table with a tray on top of it which housed our Microgreens; within this tray each Microgreen was sown in a cup with holes in the bottom to allow adequate drainage, an essential consideration, to avoid anaerobic conditions. We watered our Microgreens twice a day by hand, 8 hours apart. This can be seen in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2: Photo taken of the Danish pilot site's uncontrolled experiment for growing Microgreens in real conditions. Experiments occurred in a standard Greenhouse heated to 20 degrees.

Environmental conditions were monitored and controlled (only in the case of light and temperature) by the University's centralized software and network for controlling all greenhouses at the Taastrup campus. In collaboration with SCiO, we established an independent network and connected the GOhydro project's novel Sensor Kit. Because of the winter outdoor conditions and concomitant temperature differentials, condensation on the greenhouse glass panels was a frequent occurrence. We therefore kept the sensor kit under plastic to protect it in case of frequent top-down wetting. It is worth mentioning that the GOhydro sensor kit is water-resistant, but because of the high amount of condensation and dripping in the greenhouse, which is a phenomenon not likely to occur in households or offices where the sensor kit will be used, we opted for extra caution to ensure the integrity of the sensor kit. Overall, the sensor kit was shown to be successful, and we sent real-time data from all the sensors to Greece for their use in other project activities. The integrated sensor kit, and the various sensors, can be seen in Figure 2.2, and they were kept in close proximity to the Microgreens experiment.

2.2.1 Lighting

For lighting, we used standard High Pressure Sodium (HPS) lamps. Their use in experimental context can be seen in Figure 2.2, above. These HPS lights were set on a timer to be on from 0600 until 2200, for a photoperiod of 16 hours. As the experiments took place during the shortest daylength period of the year, the extra incidental sunlight did not likely modify the experimental results. Figure 2.2 also shows the amount of natural ambient light that occurred around 1400, which was highly attenuated, especially as most days were overcast as well. Furthermore, the average day length (hours of daylight) in Denmark in November is around 8.5 hours, while in December it is only around 7 hours. This natural fluctuation imprints our experiments with valuable information, as it more closely mimics real conditions that everyday growers would experience. This particular greenhouse environment is therefore a useful proxy for growing Microgreens in an office or semi-controlled space. Furthermore, by placing them next to windows to get incident light supplemented with a grow light given our northern latitude, we demonstrate what conditions in this part of the world would realistically look like during this time of year. At this latitude, daily light integral (DLI) is negligible with around 0 to 5 mol/m²/day. During the summer this increases up to around 35 to 45 mol/m²/day. For comparison, the DLI in northern Spain in November and December is around 16 to 12.6 mol/m²/day. In general, Microgreens need a DLI of around 12 mol/m²/day to achieve ideal growth conditions. This is why we supplemented the essentially negligible Danish DLI during the peak winter months with HPS lights. Our experimental conditions, designed to be uncontrolled, therefore only used a standard supplementary grow light (HPS) which did not react to daylength or sunlight intensity. Therefore, these experiments show what uncontrolled growing conditions in winter in northern latitudes with natural fluctuations of conditions such as Denmark can achieve. Figure 2.3 demonstrates the standard spectral components of an HPS light compared to an LED light. The essential differences can be seen as a lack of blue light, and a preponderance of yellow, around 575 nm, and orange light up to around 630 nm, with very low incidence of spectral components beyond this. It is also worth noting that, beyond the wavelength features on this figure, HPS lights also produce a significant amount of heat, while LEDs produce very little. Therefore, this is an important consideration in northern latitudes, especially those where heating is a problem during the long cold winters.

Figure 2.3: Figure detailing distribution of spectral components in two different light sources, HPS and LED.

Figure credit: Pawson and Bader, 2014.

(https://www.researchgate.net/publication/267070067_LED_lighting_increases_the_ecological_impact_of_light_pollution_irrespective_of_color_temperature)

2.2.2 Plant Material

In the Danish uncontrolled pilot site experiments, we grew three different species of Herbaceous Microgreens: Basil (*Osimum basilicum* var. Green Tesla), Pea (*Pisum sativum* var. Green Balboa) and Coriander (*Coriandrum sativum* var. Green Thunder). These Microgreens are characterized by their longer growing period and more herbaceous flavor profiles, rather than intense mustard flavors of Brassicaceae Microgreens which were grown in previous project tasks for shorter durations (Task 1.2 and 4.2, for instance). For our experiment, the seeds were sown in plastic cups, with dimensions of 10 x 14.5 x 5 cm, on 100% cellulose growing pads. As in previous experiments, we also used 100% cellulose fiber for our substrate on which we grew our Microgreens. The substrate was soaked until saturated with distilled water prior to sowing. After sowing seeds onto the soaked substrate, they were misted for approximately 1 second with distilled water to ensure initial moisture at the superior surface of the seeds. Our substrate was not compensated with a top-weight over the seeds, which was crucial for allowing the seedlings unimpeded vertical growth potential for dark-zone germination and development time of 8 days. After sowing, each of the 24 cups were allocated according to a Complete Random Block Design (CRBD). After this 8 day dark-germination period, the plants were put under the lights for 8 days of light treatment, and were therefore harvested 16 days after sowing. In the previous round of experiments, the Microgreen species were more spread out and distributed on layers in our controlled climate chamber grow system. However, for our uncontrolled experiments, we used a complete random block design (CRBD) for the entire experiment and grew them on a plastic tray under the light to mimic uncontrolled conditions. As Figure 2.2 shows, the Microgreens were spread out to avoid as much shading as possible.

Figure 2.4: Close-up photo of our uncontrolled Microgreen experiments at the Danish pilot site, with the focus on the GOhydro sensor kit featured on the left, housed in protective plastic, with the sensors situated in close proximity to the Microgreens experiment, and the three species of Microgreens grown: Pea, Coriander, and Basil.

For the first round of experiments, we did not use fertilization; for the second set of experiments, we supplemented the water with fertilizer. As is consistent with our previous work, we also grew our Microgreens at two different seeding densities to better understand the effect of space efficiency vs. competition. To achieve symmetry with our past work, we germinated the Microgreens for 8 days in the dark before having them grow under the light for 8 days, for a total growing period of 16 days. Although it is common to grow these herbaceous Microgreens at shorter and longer durations, depending on the species, we wanted to achieve harvest at the same date so we could grow multiple generations in a symmetrical manner. The 16 days is therefore the mean optimal growing period of the three different species of Microgreens that we grew (Basil, Pea, and Coriander). In previous experiments, we found that the Pea Microgreens did not achieve equal germination when they were not soaked prior to sowing. Therefore, for these experiments, we continued the practice of soaking both the Pea and the Coriander Microgreens for 24 hours before sowing them into their cups (replicates). Beyond fertilization as an experimental factor, we also varied Seeding Density for all our Microgreen species. For instance, the Basil was sown at a standard density of 1 gram per cup and a high density of 1.5 grams per cup. Coriander seeds were sown at 5 grams per cup for the standard density and 7.5 grams per cup for the high density. Pea seeds were sown at 20 grams per cup at the standard density and 28 grams per cup for high density. Essentially, the standard densities were derived from a professional grower that supplied the seeds, and we modified these sowing densities by adding an extra 50% for a high density experimental factor. At the Danish pilot site, experiments took place from November 15th to November 30th for Experiment

1, and November 30th to December 15th for Experiment 2. These seeding density values, Microgreen density per centimeter squared, and estimated Microgreens per cup can be seen in Table 2.4, below.

Figure 2.5: Photo of the three species of Microgreen—Pea, Basil, and Coriander—grown in uncontrolled environmental conditions at the Danish pilot site. The GOhydro sensor kit is protected under plastic in the background, with its sensors in close proximity to the experiment. Watering container seen in far-right of the image.

Table 2.4: 100 seed weights (+/- standard error), seeding densities in grams per cup and estimated number of seeds per cup at standard and high densities, and estimated seeds per cm² are shown

	100 Seed Weight (g)	Standard (g/cup)	Est. Seeds/cup	Seeds per cm ²	High (g/cup)	Est. Seeds/cup	Seeds per cm ²
Pea	19.52 ± 0.24	20	103.79	0.72	28	145.30	1.00
Coriander	0.90 ± 0.01	1	556.02	3.83	1.5	834.03	5.75
Basil	0.13 ± 0.001	5	759.49	5.24	7.5	1139.24	7.86

2.2.3 Environmental Conditions

As previously discussed, although only the temperature was actively controlled, and the HPS light being on automatically from 0600 to 2200, we collected data on internal and external climate parameters that were not controlled. Table 2.5 demonstrates the climatic parameters that occurred during our experiments. Namely, Outdoor Temperature (°C), Greenhouse Temperature (°C), Outdoor Solar Radiation (W/m²), Outdoor Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR; μmol), and Greenhouse Relative Humidity (RH; %). From this Table, we can see that there was a consistent control of temperature in the Greenhouse, despite changes in outdoor average temperature from 5 degrees to 0.5 degrees °C in outdoor conditions. However, just as with homes or offices, there were daily fluctuations. We can also see the 18% reduction in outdoor solar radiation and PAR as well from experiment 1 to experiment 2. However, the Greenhouse conditions were relatively stable, with only an overall average reduction of 2% for Greenhouse PAR. For relative humidity, there was around a 10% reduction from experiment 1 to experiment 2. For pH, the same tap water, unmodified, was used for the duration of Experiment 1 (November 15th to November 30th) with a value of 7.23, and an EC value of 0.66 mS/cm. The same fertilization solution was used for Experiment 2 (November 30th to December 15th), which was set and kept at 6.0 for pH, and 1.9 mS/cm for EC.

Table 2.5: Table of means for climate parameters measured for our uncontrolled experiments at the Danish pilot site conducted from November 15th to December 15th.

Time Period	Outdoor		Outdoor	Outdoor	Greenhouse	Greenhouse	pH	EC (mS/cm)
	Temp (°C)	Greenhouse Temp (°C)	Solar Radiation (W/m ²)	PAR (μmol)	PAR (μmol)	RH (%)		
Day 1-7 (Nov 15 th)	3.96	21.47	19.92	35.12	90.78	53.46	7.23	0.66
Day 8-14	6.14	21.46	9.89	14.67	77.84	57.92	7.23	0.66
Day 15-16 (Nov 30 th)	4.92	21.49	8.02	11.52	75.67	53.91	7.23	0.66
Experiment 1 Average	5.03	21.47	14.04	23.22	83.23	55.47	7.23	0.66
Day 1-7 (Nov 30 th)	3.03	21.45	7.87	11.25	75.39	52.75	6.0	1.9
Day 8-14	-1.50	21.48	14.14	23.76	85.05	47.36	6.0	1.9
Day 15-16 (Dec 15 th)	-1.04	21.51	15.10	30.21	90.64	45.22	6.0	1.9
Experiment 2 Average	0.54	21.47	11.52	19.09	81.52	49.45	6.0	1.9

The figures below elucidate in greater detail the environmental conditions that occurred during the duration of our experiments. Figure 2.6 shows the differences between the Greenhouse temperature and the outdoor temperature, which was substantial. It is important to show, given that this was our uncontrolled experiment, that there were natural diurnal variations in daily temperature inside the Greenhouse from around 20 to 26 degrees on a given day. This variation is much greater than that seen in our controlled experiments in Deliverable 1.2. Furthermore, for RH, we can see the large amount of variation across our experimental timeframe in Figure 2.7. Deviations of around 15% on a given day were not uncommon. The PAR values in figure 2.8 demonstrate the supplementation provided by the HPS lights, which were on for 16 hours per day and provided additional PAR for the Microgreens. Finally, the last figure (2.9) shows the outdoor radiation, which can be used to determine the number of sunny days the Greenhouse experienced. From this figure, we can also determine the intensity of the light on that day as well.

Figure 2.6: Scatter and line plot for Outdoor Temperature (black line, °C) and Greenhouse Temperature (red line, °C) during the duration of our experiments from November 15th to December 15th.

Figure 2.7: Scatter and line plot for Greenhouse Relative Humidity (RH; %) during the duration of our experiments from November 15th to December 15th.

Figure 2.8: Scatter and line plot for Outdoor Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR; µmol, black line) and Greenhouse PAR (µmol, red line) during the duration of our experiments from November 15th to December 15th.

Figure 2.9: Scatter and line plot for Outdoor Solar Radiation (W/m²) during the duration of our experiments from November 15th to December 15th.

2.2.4 Fertilization

For the fertilization factor of our experiment, we used Pioneer NPK (Mg) Macro Blue 14-3-23 (3) (Pioneer, Denmark) for our macro nutrient fertilizer; for our micronutrient fertilizer, we used Pioneer Micro with Iron (Pioneer, Denmark). For the concentrated fertilizer solution, we used 10 kgs of Pioneer Macro per 100 L of water, and 1 L of Pioneer Micro per 100 L of water. Table 2.6 details the initial percentages for both Macro and Micro solutions, and their corresponding concentration (in ppm) in our hydroponic solution. In addition, we used Nitric Acid to control our pH, with a Nutrient Solution pH target of 6.0 when we fertilized, as this is essential for functional utilization of the nutrients in the fertilizer solution. If the pH is uncontrolled, the compounds cannot be properly absorbed for use by the plants. For EC, we did not modify it after achieving an initial value, with fertilization, of around of 1.9 mS/cm.

For measuring pH and Electrical Conductivity (EC, mS/cm), we used a Mesur Hand Instrument (Senmatic DGT-Voltmatic, Denmark), which has a sensitivity for pH of 0.1, and for EC has a sensitivity of 0.01 for EC values under 2.5 mS/cm. For our uncontrolled experiments at the Danish pilot site, we found that the average pH was 6.0, with the average EC being 1.9, according to preset standards for our fertilized generations. For experiments without any fertilization, the pH was around 7.23, and the EC was around 0.66. In these uncontrolled experiments, the pH was not corrected beyond initial values (6.0 for fertilization for appropriate nutrient uptake, and 7.23 for non-fertilized experiments).

Table 2.6: Fertilization details for the different macro- and micro-nutrient products used. Here we show the name, elemental sign, original concentration (%), and concentration in solution (ppm).

<i>Pioneer NPK (Mg) Macro Blue 14-3-23 (3)</i>			
<i>Description</i>	<i>Element</i>	<i>Original Concentration (%)</i>	<i>PPM in solution</i>
Total Nitrogen	N	14.00%	136.85
Nitrate	NO ₃ ⁻	10.40%	101.66
Ammonium	NH ₄ ⁺	3.60%	35.19
Water soluble Phosphorous	P	2.90%	28.35
Citric and water soluble Phosphorous	P	2.90%	28.35
Water soluble Potassium	K	23.00%	224.83
Water soluble Magnesium	Mg	3.00%	29.33
Water soluble Sulphur	S	3.90%	38.12
Chloride	Cl	0.50%	4.89
Fluoride	F	0.50%	4.89
Calcium (CaCO ₃ , Chalk, in Danish Tap Water)	Ca	X	136.85
EC (mS/cm)		1.86	

<i>Pioneer Micro with Iron</i>			
<i>Description</i>	<i>Element</i>	<i>Original Concentration (%)</i>	<i>PPM in solution</i>
Boron	B	0.23%	0.20
Copper	Cu	0.14%	0.12
Iron	Fe	1.32%	1.12
Manganese	Mn	0.50%	0.43
Molybdenum	Mo	0.05%	0.04
Zinc	Zn	0.18%	0.15
EC (mS/cm)		0.004	
Total EC (mS/cm)		1.87	

2.2.5 Biomass and Morphometric Measurements

For each experimental generation of Microgreens, 16 days after sowing, the entirety of above-substrate plant biomass (cotyledons and stem) was harvested. Fresh Weights (FW) were collected for each complete cup as an experimental replicate using a gravimetric scale with a sensitivity of $d = 0.01 / 0.001$ gram and maximum of 510 grams (PG503-S DeltaRange, Mettler Toledo, USA). Figure 2.10 shows the Microgreens when they are nearly ready for harvest. After the total FW was taken, the samples were then immediately placed in a drying oven for four days at 60 °C. The Dry Weight (DW) was then taken for each sample using the same scale. Dry Weight Percent (%) was simply calculated as the Dry Weight value (in grams) divided by the Fresh Weight value (in grams). We also took morphometric measures as well. For instance, we took measures of heights of each replicate of Microgreens grown for each experiment, with values in centimeters. According to the methodology established in Deliverable 4.1, we classified the health of each replicate of Microgreens as well, on a scale of 1 to 9, 1 being the healthiest, and 9 being the least healthy. We also counted the number of leaves for a subset of Microgreens per replicate. Finally, we also took measures of leaf area as well (cm^2). We did this using an algorithm that uses images of leaves as an input, and uses a reference square of known surface area to compare to leaves spatial footprint to. The leaves were removed from the stem and laid on white paper next to this reference square, after which photographs were taken for input into the algorithm.

Figure 2.10: Photo showing the Microgreens near the time of harvest; their apparent yellowish coloring is due to the high yellow component of HPS light spectral components.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1 USAMV RESULTS

3.1.1 Data obtained in the experiments with basil and lettuce

The methodology used for the research was the one described in the deliverable D4.1 Trial protocols for microgreens production in hydroponic units. The images of the two experiments are presented in Figure 3.1 (basil) and Figure 3.2 (lettuce).

Figure 3.1: Images of the experiment with basil in operational environmental conditions

Figure 3.2: Images of the experiment with lettuce in operational environmental conditions

The raw data collected from the two experiments are presented in table 3.1 and table 3.2 for basil and in table 3.3 and table 3.4 for lettuce.

Table 3.1: Parameters collected related to the growth environment in the basil experiment

Parameter	Unit of measurement	Specification	Day 1 /4.11	Day 2 /5.11	Day 3 /6.11	Day 4 /7.11	Day 5 /8.11	Day 6 /9.11	Day 7 /10.11	Day 8 /11.11	Day 9 /12.11	Day 10 /13.11	Day 11 /14.11	Day 12/15.11	Day 13 /16.11	Day 14 /17.11	Day 15 /18.11	Day 16 /19.11	Day 17 /20.11	Day 18 /21.11
A. Monitoring the environmental conditions – by Crop Heath Sensor Kit (CHSK)																				
Air Temperature Sensor*	°C	min/max/mean	17/24/21	17/25/21	18/25/22	19/25/22	20/25/23	20/24/22	19/25/22	20/23/22	20/22/21	20/22/21	20/22/21	20/23/22	18/23/21	19/22/21	19/22/21	18/23/21	18/23/21	18/23/21
Air Humidity Sensor*	%	min/max/mean	61/68/65	61/69/65	61/69/65	61/69/65	60/70/65	59/70/65	61/69/65	59/68/64	59/68/64	59/67/62	59/67/62	59/68/64	61/69/65	59/68/64	59/68/64	61/69/65	61/69/65	61/69/65
Light Sensor (UV)	µmolm-2s-1	lux	-	-	-	941 - 1645	941 - 1645	912 - 1621	484 - 1590	484 - 1590	484 - 1590	342 - 1490	342 - 1490	342 - 1490	342 - 1490	250-1354	250-1354	142-1245	142-1245	142-1245
B. Monitoring the water and nutrient quality – by Crop Heath Sensor Kit (CHSK) and Nutrient Content Kit (NCK)																				
Water Temperature Sensor	°C	min/max/mean	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20
Digital pH Meter***	pH units		6.8	6.8	6.8	6.9	6.9	7.0	7.0	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9
Electroconductivity Sensor	mS		1.4	1.4	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.4	1.5	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Nutrient Content Kit (NCK)	Nutrient content	*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Dissolved oxygen	mgL-1		6.5	6.5	6.5	6.5	6.5	6.8	6.6	6.4	6.4	6.4	6.4	6.4	6.4	6.4	6.3	6.3	6.3	6.3

Note: * Drinking water measurements: pH=6.81, EC=261 µS/cm, TDS=389 ppm, Nitrites NO₂ = 0 mg/l, Nitrates NO₃ = 0 mg/l, Hardness = 14 °d

Table 3.2: Weather conditions in the area/period testing in the basil experiment

Parameter	Unit of measurement	Day 1 /4.11	Day 2 /5.11	Day 3 /6.11	Day 4 /7.11	Day 5 /8.11	Day 6 /9.11	Day 7 /10.11	Day 8 /11.11	Day 9 /12.11	Day 10 /13.11	Day 11 /14.11	Day 12 /15.11	Day 13 /16.11	Day 14 /17.11	Day 15 /18.11	Day 16 /19.11	Day 17 /20.11	Day 18 /21.11
Minimum temperature	°C	17	17	18	19	20	20	19	20	20	20	20	20	18	19	19	18	18	18
Maximum temperature	°C	24	25	25	25	25	24	25	23	22	22	22	23	23	22	22	23	23	23
Mean temperature	°C	21	21	22	22	23	22	22	22	21	21	21	22	21	21	21	21	21	21
Minimum atmospheric humidity	%	61	61	61	61	60	59	61	59	59	59	59	59	61	59	59	61	61	61
Maximum atmospheric humidity	%	68	69	69	69	70	70	69	68	68	67	67	68	69	68	68	69	69	69
Mean atmospheric humidity	%	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	64	64	62	62	64	65	64	64	65	65	65

Table 3.3: Parameters collected related to the growth environment in the lettuce experiment

Note: * Drinking water measurements: pH=6.81, EC=261 µS/cm, TDS=389 ppm, Nitrites NO₂ = 0 mg/l, Nitrates NO₃ = 0 mg/l, Hardness = 14 °d

Table 3.4: Weather conditions in the area/period testing in the lettuce experiment

Parameter	Unit of measurement	Specification	Day 1 /5.12	Day 2 /6.12	Day 3 /7.12	Day 4 /8.12	Day 5 /9.12	Day 6 /10.12	Day 7 /11.12	Day 8 /12.12	Day 9 /13.12	Day 10 /14.12	Day 11 /15.12	Day 12/16.12	Day 13 /17.12	Day 14 /18.12	Day 15 /19.12
A. Monitoring the environmental conditions – by Crop Heath Sensor Kit (CHSK)																	
Air Temperature Sensor*	°C	min/max/mean	20/22/21	19/21/20	20/22/21	19/21/20	21/23/22	21/23/22	21/23/22	21/23/22	21/22/21	21/22/21	21/22/21	20/21/21	20/21/21	20/21/21	20/21/21
Air Humidity Sensor*	%	min/max/mean	57/60/63	56/58/57	56/59/58	56/58/57	56/58/57	56/58/57	56/58/57	55/57/56	55/57/56	55/57/56	55/57/56	54/56/55	54/56/55	54/56/55	54/56/55
Light Sensor (UV)	µmolm-2s-1	lux	-	-	-	140-1213	140-1213	140-1213	140-1213	140-1213	135-1142	135-1142	135-1142	135-1142	135-1142	135-1142	135-1142
B. Monitoring the water and nutrient quality – by Crop Heath Sensor Kit (CHSK) and Nutrient Content Kit (NCK)																	
Water Temperature Sensor	°C	min/max/mean	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	20/22/21	20/22/21	20/22/21	21/23/22	20/22/21	20/22/21	20/22/21	20/21/21	20/21/21	20/21/21	20/21/21
Digital pH Meter	pH units		6.8	6.8	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.8	6.8	6.8	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9
Electroconductivity Sensor	mS		1.4	1.4	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4
Nutrient Content Kit (NCK)	Nutrient content	*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Dissolved oxygen	mgL-1		6.5	6.4	6.5	6.5	6.5	6.5	6.5	6.5	6.4	6.4	6.4	6.4	6.4	6.4	6.4

Parameter	Unit of measurement	Day 1 /5.12	Day 2 /6.12	Day 3 /7.12	Day 4 /8.12	Day 5 /9.12	Day 6 /10.12	Day 7 /11.12	Day 8 /12.12	Day 9 /13.12	Day 10 /14.12	Day 11 /15.12	Day 12/16.12	Day 13 /17.12	Day 14 /18.12	Day 15 /19.12
Minimum temperature	°C	20	19	20	19	21	21	21	21	21	21	21	20	20	20	20
Maximum temperature	°C	22	21	22	21	23	23	23	23	22	22	22	21	21	21	21
Mean temperature	°C	21	20	21	20	22	22	22	22	21	21	21	21	21	21	21
Minimum atmospheric humidity	%	57	56	56	56	56	56	56	55	55	55	55	54	54	54	54
Maximum atmospheric humidity	%	60	58	59	58	58	58	58	57	57	57	57	56	56	56	56
Mean atmospheric humidity	%	63	57	58	57	57	57	57	56	56	56	56	55	55	55	55

The influence of the environmental conditions outside the microgreens cultivation spaces can influence the conditions inside the houses and the development of microgreens. That is why the external environmental data were also analyzed, using for this purpose the data collected by Meteo Romania: <https://www.meteoromania.ro/grafice/>.

The external environmental conditions from the basil experimentation period, November 2022, are presented in Figure 3.3 (accessed 12/12/2022), and from the lettuce experimentation period, December 2022, are presented in Figure 3.4 (accessed 03/01/2023).

a. Outside atmospheric humidity (1-30/11/2022)

b. Outside air temperature (1-30/11/2022)

c. Outside total cloudiness (1-30/11/2022)

Figure 3.3: External environmental conditions during the basil experimentation period

a. Outside atmospheric humidity (1-31/12/2022)

b. Outside air temperature (1-31/12/2022)

c. Outside total cloudiness (1-31/12/2022)

Figure 3.4: External environmental conditions during the lettuce experimentation period

The growth of microgreens and their production is presented in table 3.5 for basil and in table 3.6 for lettuce.

Table 3.5: Parameters related to microgreen growth, production and quality in the basil experiment			
Parameter	Unit of measurement	Day 18/21.11	Day 18/21.11
Determining the health state of plants		Germaline	Grand Vert
Intensity of the disease attack	Note 1-9	1	1
Measurements on the morphology of plants*		r1/r2/r3	r1/r2/r3
Stem length	mm	35.2/34.1/31.1	28.4/28.2/25.2
Internode length	mm	35.2/34.1/31.1	28.4/28.2/25.2
Number of leaves	no	2 / 2 / 2	2 / 2 / 2
Number of plants	no/cm ²	10.3 / 9.8 / 10.1	9.6 / 8.9 / 8.6
Leaves area (10 plants per tray)	cm ²	0.61 / 0.59 / 0.58	0.52 / 0.53 / 0.50
Determining Fresh Biomass Yield and Dry Matter Content			
Fresh Weight	g tray (992 cm ²)	89.41/87.75/85.74	77.41/75.42/74.56
Dry Weight	g tray (992 cm ²)	9.01/8.85/8.74	7.84/7.67/7.56
Total phenols	mg/kg	106/109/108	109/127/118

Note: r1- top tray; r2 - middle tray; r3 - bottom tray

Table 3.6: Parameters related to microgreen growth, production and quality in the lettuce experiment				
Parameter	Unit of measurement	Day 15 /19.12	Day 15/19.12	Day 15/19.12
Determining the health state of plants		Paris White	Little Gem	Lolla Rossa
Intensity of the disease attack	Note 1-9	4	1	1
Measurements on the morphology of plants*		r1/r2/r3	r1/r2/r3	r1/r2/r3
Stem length	mm	0/0/0	31.4/31.8/32.4	32.4/31.9/32.8
Internode length	mm	0/0/0	31.4/31.8/32.4	32.4/31.9/32.8
Number of leaves	no	0/0/0	2.5/2.4/2.6	2.3/2.1/2.2
Number of plants	no/cm ²	0/0/0	10.4/10.2/10.3	9.6/9.5/9.8
Leaves area (10 plants per tray)	cm ²	0/0/0	0.51/0.49/0.50	0.61/0.59/0.64
Determining Fresh Biomass Yield and Dry Matter Content				
Fresh Weight	g tray (661 cm ²)	0/0/0	47.24/48.21/47.54	54.12/55.84/55.45
Dry Weight	g tray (661 cm ²)	0/0/0	3.27/3.34/3.29	3.75/3.87/3.84
Total phenols	mg/kg	0/0/0	98/101/97	104/101/105

Note: r1- top tray; r2 - middle tray; r3 - bottom tray

The growing conditions of the two species of microgreens (basil and lettuce) it is specific to the conditions in the operational environment, being also influenced by the external environmental conditions, respectively especially by cloudiness. Thus, a temperature was kept in the atmosphere with a oscillation of 3-7 °C, an atmospheric humidity oscillation of 8-15 %, and respectively a variable amount of light (of 135-1645 μmolm⁻²s⁻¹).

The irrigation water had a constant temperature of 19-21 °C, a pH of 6.8-7, an electrical conductivity between 1.4-1.5 mS, and respectively a quantity of 6.4-6.5 mg L⁻¹ dissolved oxygen.

No nutrients were used for fertigation.

3.1.2 Fresh Weight Accumulation

The amount of Fresh Weight (FW) depends on both the cultivated species and the variety (Table 3.7), respectively its suitability for hydroponic microgreens. Among the 2 species tested, lettuce ensures distinctly significantly positive Fresh Weight production (Table 3.8). By comparison with the Duncan test (Table 3.9), it results that the best amount of Fresh Weight is provided by Basil - Germaline Basilic Bio, with 883.40 g/m².

Table 3.7: The amount of Fresh Weight Accumulation in the two species (basil and lettuce) and varieties

Species	Variety	Repetition (g/m ²)		
		R1	R2	R3
Basil	Germaline Basilic Bio	901.31	884.58	864.32
	Grand Vert	780.34	760.28	751.61
Lettuce	Little Gem	714.67	729.35	719.21
	Lolla Rossa	818.76	844.78	838.88

Table 3.8: The influence of the species on the amount of Fresh Weight Accumulation

Species	Fresh Weight		Difference ±	Significance
	g/m ²	%		
Control	800.67	100	Ct.	Ct.
Basil	823.74	102.9	23.07	-
Lettuce	777.61	97.1	-23.07	-

Note: DL (p 5%)= 60.68 g/m²; DL (p 1%)= 140.14 g/m²; DL(p 0.1%)= 445.95 g/m²

Table 3.9: Synthesis of comparisons through the Duncan test

Species and variety	Fresh Weight, g/m ²	Classification
Lettuce - Little Gem	721.08	a
Basil - Grand Vert	764.08	b
Lettuce - Lolla Rossa	834.14	c
Basil - Germaline Basilic Bio	883.40	d

3.1.3 Dry Weight Accumulation

Following the statistical processing of the data (ANOVA) regarding Dry Weight Accumulation, it is found that the results differ from Fresh Weight. The results obtained on the repetitions (GOhydro platform trays) are presented in the Table 3.10. Basil provides the highest amount of Dry Weight (DW) (Table 3.11), with a distinctly significantly positive difference compared to the control (average). The same results after processing the data with the Duncan test, respectively the 2 varieties of basil ensure the highest Dry Weight results (Table 3.12).

Table 3.10: The amount of Dry Weight Accumulation in the two species (basil and lettuce) and varieties

Species	Variety	Repetition (g/m ²)		
		R1	R2	R3
Basil	Germaline Basilic Bio	90.83	89.21	88.10
	Grand Vert	79.03	77.32	76.21
Lettuce	Little Gem	49.47	50.53	49.77
	Lolla Rossa	56.73	58.55	58.09

Table 3.11: The influence of the species on the amount of Dry Weight Accumulation

Species	Dry Weight		Difference ±	Significance
	g/m ²	%		
Control	68.65	100	Ct.	Ct.
Basil	83.45	121.6	14.80	**
Lettuce	53.86	78.4	-14.80	00

Note: DL (p 5%)= 4.85 g/m²; DL (p 1%)= 11.20 g/m²; DL(p 0.1%)= 35.63 g/m²

Table 3.12: Synthesis of comparisons through the Duncan test

Species and variety	Dry Weight, g/m ²	Classification
Lettuce - Little Gem	49.92	a
Lettuce - Lolla Rossa	57.79	b
Basil - Grand Vert	77.52	c
Basil - Germaline Basilic Bio	89.38	d

3.1.4 Total Phenolics/Morphology

The results obtained in the case of total phenols are presented in the Table 3.13. The variability of the data recorded for total phenols is very high, the statistical processing does not highlight results with a significant difference (Table 3.14). Lettuce contains 98-105 mg/kg, and basil 106-127 mg/kg total phenols (Table 3.15).

Table 3.13: The amount of total phenols in the two species (basil and lettuce) and varieties

Species	Variety	Repetition (mg/kg)		
		R1	R2	R3
Basil	Germaline Basilic Bio	106	109	108
	Grand Vert	109	127	118
Lettuce	Little Gem	98	101	97
	Lolla Rossa	104	101	105

Table 3.14: The influence of the species on the amount of total phenols

Species	Total phenols		Difference ±	Significance
	mg/kg	%		
Control	106.92	100	Ct.	Ct.
Basil	112.83	105.5	5.92	-
Lettuce	101.00	94.5	-5.92	-

Note: DL (p 5%)= 13.04 g/m²; DL (p 1%)= 30.11 g/m²; DL(p 0.1%)= 95.82 g/m²

Table 3.15: Synthesis of comparisons through the Duncan test

Species and variety	Total phenols, mg/kg	Classification
Lettuce - Little Gem	98.67	a
Lettuce - Lolla Rossa	103.33	a
Basil - Germaline Basilic Bio	107.67	a
Basil - Grand Vert	118.00	b

From the morphological analysis of plant development, both in basil and in lettuce, no disease attack is registered, due to the maintenance of the health of the water in the feed basin and a quantity of around 6.4-6.5 mg L⁻¹ of dissolved oxygen. An exception is made in the case of lettuce, the Paris White variety, which registers until the end, grade 4 in the degree of attack. Due to the higher thermal oscillations than in the case of the experiment under controlled conditions, the degree of attack was slightly higher. This is due exclusively to this variety in which the seed had an inadequate quality for the production of hydroponic microgreens. There

are differences regarding the number of leaves, the length of the microgreens, etc. but these are given in particular by the variety used. Within the same variety, the differences between repetitions were very small, insignificant.

Results obtained in the experiment regarding the influence of the substrate type

The obtained productions are presented in the table 3.16.

Table 3.16: Influence of substrate type on fresh biomass yield

No.	Species	The amount of seed on the tray (g)* (side length 10.5 cm), s = 110.25 cm ²	Substrate type	Fresh biomass, g	Harvest period, days
1	White cabbage: Golden Acre Cabbage – <i>Brassica oleracea</i> var. <i>Capitata</i>	0.89	Jute	5.41	15
			Pads	7.52	
			Felt	3.85	
			Hemp	3.54	
2	Broccoli: Waltham 29 Broccoli – <i>Brassica oleracea</i> var. <i>Italica</i>	1.13	Jute	7.09	15
			Pads	7.47	
			Felt	6.97	
			Hemp	5.36	
3	Mustard: Mizuna Red Streaks Mustard – <i>Brassica rapa</i> var. <i>Japonica</i>	0.67	Jute	3.75	13
			Pads	4.17	
			Felt	3.80	
			Hemp	4.18	
4	Radish: Sango Purple Sprouting Radish – <i>Raphanus sativus</i>	1.74	Jute	7.22	7
			Pads	9.24	
			Felt	8.70	
			Hemp	8.43	

*Determined with Microgreens Seed Calculator Francesco Di Gioia: <https://extension.psu.edu/microgreens-seed-density-calculator>

Figure 3.5: Influence of substrate type on the production of microgreens, under hydroponic conditions and in the operational environment

The conclusions of the experiment, which require the optimization of production procedures with the GOhydro platform, are:

- The influence of the substrate on the yield of fresh biomass was as follows: Pads = 4.17-9.24 g; Felt = 3.80-8.70 g; Hemp = 3.54-8.42 g; Jute = 3.75-7.09 g.
- All cultures had too low a density, due to the unknown percentage of germination:
 - the amount of seed on the tray was determined with the Francesco Di Gioia Microgreens Seed Calculator;
 - a standard germination of 90% was considered;
 - the actual germination was about 60-70%;
 - it is necessary to know / determine the actual germination of the seeds.
- Microgreens attacked by pathogens were identified:

- the seeds must first be sterilized by soaking for 2 minutes in 80% ethanol, rinsed twice with distilled water and then dried in an oven at 45°C for 40 minutes (Tavan et al., 2021).
4. The seeds were moistened differently:
- it is necessary to wet the seeds in advance.

3.2 UCPH RESULTS

3.2.1 Grouped ANOVA Results for Uncontrolled Experiments

When we grouped our entire dataset for initial analysis, we found that there were many significant effects for our parameters of interest (Table 3.17). For instance, we found that Fertilizer was always highly significant and that Seeding Density was important for FW and DW accumulation, but not for DW% or Height. Species was also highly significant for all parameters. We also found that Fertilizer by Seeding Density was not ever significant, but whenever Species was an interactive factor, it was significant for 75% of the time at the second order interaction. For third order, there were no significant effects on our four parameters of interest. Therefore, we unnested our dataset and conducted analyses separately for each of our three species to better demonstrate the nuances and sensitivities of these different species to our experimental factors. This is consistent biologically, as we have three different genres and species grown in our experiments which will have different responses to our experimental factors according to their particular life histories. We can see these differences in Table 3.18, which is a summary of means +/- standard error for our six parameters of interest, separated by species.

Table 3.17: ANOVA results for all species grouped together as one dataset. Columns show p-values for each of our variables of interest: Fresh Weight per Unit Area (FW; kg/m²), Rel FW (g/cup/g seed), Dry Weight per Unit Area (DW; kg/m²), Rel DW (g/cup/g seed) Dry Weight Percent (DW, %), and Height (cm).

Effects	FW (kg/m ²)	Rel FW (g/cup/g seed)	DW (kg/m ²)	Rel DW (g/cup/g seed)	DW% (%)	Height (cm)
Species	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
Fertilizer	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.001	< 0.01	< 0.001	< 0.001
Seeding Density	< 0.001	0.48	< 0.001	< 0.01	0.09	0.58
Fertilizer:Seeding Density	0.62	0.26	0.70	0.06	0.40	0.74
Fertilizer:Species	0.02	0.01	0.05	0.02	< 0.001	< 0.001
Seeding Density:Species	< 0.001	0.91	< 0.001	0.02	0.24	0.96
Fertilizer:Seeding Density:Species	0.91	0.09	0.62	0.37	0.20	0.73

Table 3.18: Summary table of means +/- standard error for our three species, Basil, Coriander, and Pea, detailing results for Fresh Weight, Relative FW, Dry Weight, Relative DW, Dry Weight %, Health, Height, and Leaf Area in our uncontrolled Danish pilot site experiments.

Values	Basil	Cilantro	Pea
Fresh Weight (kg/m ²)	0.62 ± 0.03	2.42 ± 0.15	4.39 ± 0.18
Rel FW (g/cup/g seed)	6.94 ± 0.15	5.42 ± 0.20	2.57 ± 0.05
Dry Weight (kg/m ²)	0.03 ± 0.00	0.24 ± 0.01	0.42 ± 0.02
Rel DW (g/cup/g seed)	0.36 ± 0.01	0.53 ± 0.01	0.24 ± 0.00
Dry Weight (%)	0.05 ± 0.00	0.10 ± 0.00	0.10 ± 0.00
Health (1-9 pt. scale)	1.25 ± 0.13	1.00 ± 0.00	1.82 ± 0.12
Height (cm)	3.9 ± 0.05	9.58 ± 0.15	20.66 ± 0.38
Leaf Area (cm ²)	2.26 ± 0.31	3.59 ± 0.49	16.72 ± 0.84

3.2.2 Fresh Weight per Area (kilograms per meter²)

After demonstrating the importance of unnesting our analysis according to species, we conducted a series of ANOVAs for each of our Microgreen species grown in our experiments. Table 3.19 below demonstrates the results of our ANOVA analysis for the uncontrolled experiments at the Danish pilot site. We found that for Coriander, there was a highly significant influence of fertilization ($p < 0.01$) and seeding density ($p < 0.001$), but not their interaction, on fresh weight accumulation. For Basil, the higher order interaction between Fertilizer and Seeding Density was significant ($p = 0.03$). For Pea, only Seeding Density was significant ($p < 0.001$). We therefore showed that there are distinct species-specific responses to the different environmental conditions.

Table 3.19: ANOVA results for Coriander, Basil, and Pea Microgreen Fresh Weight per Unit Area (kg/m²) based on Fertilizer application, Microgreen Seeding Density, and their interaction (Fertilizer:Seeding Density).

Fresh Weight (kg/m ²) Effects	Coriander P-Value	Basil P-Value	Pea P-Value
Fertilizer	< 0.01	0.57	0.42
Seeding Density	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
Fertilizer:Seeding Density	0.75	0.03	0.94

To better demonstrate the directionality of the relationships revealed by our ANOVAs, we created visualizations using a bar plot with standard error, combined with a compact letter display (CLD) of Tukey’s Honestly Significant Difference (HSD; $p=0.05$) to show intra-species differences according to the experimental factor. As Figure 3.6 demonstrates below, Basil had significant differences according to seeding density, with less influence of fertilization on accumulation. For Coriander, both Fertilizer and Seeding Density were significant predictors of FW accumulation. Unsurprisingly, fertilization was associated with increased FW accumulation, as was the higher seeding density. For Pea, Figure 3.6 shows that there were primarily significant differences between Seeding Density. However, on average fertilization was also higher than non-fertilized Pea treatments. Across species, we can also see that Basil produced by far the least amount of biomass, with Coriander in the middle, and Pea producing the most. Overall Basil was around 4 times less productive compared to Coriander, and about 7 times less productive than Pea. Pea produced around 1.8 times the Fresh Weight of Coriander. However, Pea was sown with 20 or 28 grams compared to 5 or 7.5 grams for Coriander.

Figure 3.6: Bar plot for Fresh Weight per unit area (kg/m²) for Basil (blue and purple), Cilantro (green and gray), and Pea (orange and yellow) with standard errors (+/-) and compact letter displays derived from Tukey’s HSD ($p=0.05$). Darker colors are for high density, and lighter are for standard density, with each color corresponding to a fertilization group (Yes or No).

3.2.3 Relative Fresh Weight (grams/cup/gram seed)

Although total FW produced per unit area is a very informative metric, it can also be useful to demonstrate how the production of FW is a function of the starting seed weight that was sown. This can offer important information about the relative production of FW, as comparing seeding densities without modification (into relative terms) can obscure important context. Therefore, we have taken our FW values (in grams per cup) and divided them by their starting seed weight. The ANOVA table (3.20) below demonstrates essentially the same degree of variance and significance as the table for FW (kg/m²), but was overall less significant with all three species losing their significant Seeding Density effect. This demonstrates that it is important to also consider relative production when determining optimal scenarios for Microgreen production.

Table 3.20: ANOVA results for Coriander, Basil, and Pea Relative Fresh Weight (grams/cup/gram seed) based on Fertilizer application, Microgreen Seeding Density, and their interaction (Fertilizer:Seeding Density).

Fresh Weight (grams/cup/gram seed) Effects	Coriander P-Value	Basil P-Value	Pea P-Value
Fertilizer	0.01	0.93	0.05
Seeding Density	0.93	0.53	0.09
Fertilizer:Seeding Density	0.73	0.04	0.69

Figure 3.7 expands on the ANOVA results discussed above by demonstrating the impact of relativizing Seeding Density when discussing optimal Microgreen production. Overall, we can see that for Coriander and Pea, there are very minor differences in relative production according to Seeding Density. This means that our growing environments were not too competitive, as we did not see a loss of productivity in either Pea or Coriander at higher Seeding Densities. However, we can see that fertilization did have a significant effect on relative biomass production, with Fertilization improving the biomass production, significantly, for both Pea and Coriander. Tukey’s HSD, being more conservative than the ANOVA, shows significance across grouped fertilized means, or non-fertilized means, but is not sensitive to the unnested fertilization within seeding density. For Basil, the results are a bit more nuanced, which reflects the significant higher order interactive effect (p=0.04). We can see that at a higher density for Basil, fertilization was associated with greater gains than at the lower density, where fertilization was actually negatively associated with relative production at the standard density. This could be the result of health impacts due to fertilization, to which Basil is quite sensitive.

Figure 3.7: Bar plot for Relative Fresh Weight (grams/cup/gram seed) for Basil (blue and purple), Cilantro (green and gray), and Pea (orange and yellow) with standard errors (+/-) and compact letter displays derived from Tukey’s HSD (p=0.05). Darker colors are for high density, and lighter are for standard density, with each color corresponding to a fertilization group (Yes or No).

3.2.4 Dry Weight per Area (kilograms per meter²)

Following the unnested species analysis for FW in section 3.2.2, we conducted the same level of analysis for Dry Weight per unit area (kg/m²). Table 3.21 shows the ANOVA results from this analysis. For Coriander, we found that both Fertilizer and Seeding Density were significant (p < 0.01 and p < 0.001, respectively), with their interaction once again not being significant. For Basil, similarly to FW, we found that Seeding Density was significant, but for DW there was no significant interaction like there was for FW. For Pea, both Fertilizer (p=0.03) and Seeding Density (p < 0.001) were significant. Overall, we showed that there were very similar dynamics for DW as there were for FW, but once again with species-specific dynamics.

Table 3.21: ANOVA results for Coriander, Basil, and Pea Microgreen Dry Weight per Unit Area (kg/m²) based on Fertilizer application, Microgreen Seeding Density, and their interaction (Fertilizer:Seeding Density).

Dry Weight (kg/m ²) Effects	Coriander P-Value	Basil P-Value	Pea P-Value
Fertilizer	< 0.01	0.62	0.03
Seeding Density	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
Fertilizer:Seeding Density	0.35	0.31	0.75

Figure 3.8 shows a more detailed demonstration of the directionality of relationships within our three species of Microgreens for Dry Weight per unit area (kg/m²). For Basil, we can see that Seeding Density explained the most variation. For Coriander, Figure 3.8 shows that fertilizer had a negative impact on Dry Weight accumulation, with the most variation explained by Seeding Density. A similar pattern was seen for Pea, whereby fertilization had a negative effect on Dry Weight accumulation, with Seeding Density also explaining more variation. Similarly to the results for Fresh Weight, Basil produced around 8 times less Dry Weight compared to Coriander, and about 14 times less Dry Weight compared to Pea. Pea produced around 1.75 times the Dry Weight of Coriander as well, which is essentially the same factor as for FW.

Figure 3.8: Bar plot for Dry Weight per unit area (kg/m²) for Basil (blue and purple), Cilantro (green and gray), and Pea (orange and yellow) with standard errors (+/-) and compact letter displays derived from Tukey’s HSD (p=0.05). Darker colors are for high density, and lighter are for standard density, with each color corresponding to a fertilization group (Yes or No).

3.2.5 Relative Dry Weight (grams/cup/gram seed)

In the same manner as done for the relativized Fresh Weight (grams/cup/gram seed) done in section 3.2.3 above, we also conducted an ANOVA for relativized Dry Weight (grams/cup/gram seed), the results of which are seen in Table 3.22. Once again, the Coriander and Pea Microgreens lost the significance of their Seeding Density effect, just as with relative Fresh Weight. However, for Basil, it retained its significance at Seeding Density ($p < 0.01$). Coriander relative Dry Weight was still significantly associated with Fertilizer application. For Pea, no such effect was seen, which is another example of a lost significance effect when controlling for Seeding Density. These results show the importance of considering the relative and nuanced nature of Microgreen production; both production outputs required, and their particular form, must be considered within the constraints of biology and the given productive system. Here, we have shown that relative production is an important, sensitive metric that offers a novel lens into the production of Microgreens.

Table 3.22: ANOVA results for Coriander, Basil, and Pea Microgreen Relative Dry Weight (grams/cup/gram seed) based on Fertilizer application, Microgreen Seeding Density, and their interaction (Fertilizer:Seeding Density).

Relative Dry Weight (grams/cup/gram seed) Effects	Coriander P-Value	Basil P-Value	Pea P-Value
Fertilizer	< 0.001	0.51	0.47
Seeding Density	0.61	< 0.01	0.11
Fertilizer:Seeding Density	0.07	0.29	0.89

Figure 3.9 below demonstrates the directionality of effects described in Table 3.22. For instance, we can see the impact of fertilization on Coriander relative DW production, with fertilization having an overall negative effect. Interestingly, we can see that for Coriander, the standard density was higher than the high density, indicating a superior relative production. We see the same effect for Pea, although to a smaller degree. Finally, for Basil, we can also see the same effect whereby the Standard Seeding Density was significantly higher than the High Seeding Density. Therefore, this is an important elaboration of the DW accumulation information discussed in the previous section. We have shown here that, as was the case with relative FW, relative DW offers new information into the productive dynamics of Microgreens.

Figure 3.9: Bar plot for Relative Dry Weight (grams/cup/gram seed) for Basil (blue and purple), Cilantro (green and gray), and Pea (orange and yellow) with standard errors (+/-) and compact letter displays derived from Tukey’s HSD ($p=0.05$). Darker colors are for high density, and lighter are for standard density, with each color corresponding to a fertilization group (Yes or No).

3.2.6 Dry Weight Percentage (%)

For Dry Weight Percentage, we divided the Dry Weight biomass by the Fresh Weight biomass to understand how much of our material that we grew was non-water based. This is important to understand the different allocation pathways of our treatments, both for fertilization and Seeding Density. For instance, Table 3.23 shows that for Coriander, only Fertilizer was significant ($p < 0.001$) as a factor influencing Dry Weight %. For Basil, only Seeding Density showed significance ($p < 0.01$). Finally, for Pea, only Fertilizer was significant for Dry Weight % ($p < 0.001$).

Table 3.23: ANOVA results for Coriander, Basil, and Pea Microgreen Dry Weight Percentage (%) based on Fertilizer application, Microgreen Seeding Density, and their interaction (Fertilizer:Seeding Density).

Dry Weight Percentage (%) Effects	Coriander P-Value	Basil P-Value	Pea P-Value
Fertilizer	< 0.001	0.36	< 0.001
Seeding Density	0.61	< 0.01	0.59
Fertilizer:Seeding Density	0.24	0.22	0.63

Figure 3.10 shows the directionality of the relationships described in the ANOVA Table above. For instance, we can see that Basil has a significant difference between Seeding Densities where the Standard density had a higher Dry Weight % compared to the High density, which could indicate a response to competition. For Coriander, we saw a different effect whereby Fertilization had the greatest influence on Dry Weight %, with application of fertilizer resulting in significantly lower Dry Weight % levels. For Pea, the same relationship was seen whereby fertilization resulted in significantly lower Dry Weight % levels. On average, Pea had 1.8 times the Dry Weight %, while Coriander had 1.9 times the Dry Weight % compared to Basil. Pea produced around 95% of the Dry Weight % values compared to Coriander. Although Pea had less variation in Dry Weight %, Coriander had the highest overall Dry Weight %.

Figure 3.10: Bar plot for Dry Weight Percentage (%) for Basil (blue and purple), Cilantro (green and gray), and Pea (orange and yellow) with standard errors (+/-) and compact letter displays derived from Tukey's HSD ($p=0.05$). Darker colors are for high density, and lighter are for standard density, with each color corresponding to a fertilization group (Yes or No).

3.2.7 Height (cm)

Beyond biomass accumulation or partitioning, we also wanted to investigate the impact of our experimental factors on morphological features, such as height. Table 3.24 shows the ANOVA results of this analysis. Overall, it shows that for Coriander, only Fertilizer significantly influenced height ($p < 0.001$). For Basil, only Seeding Density was significant ($p = 0.05$), while for Pea, only Fertilizer was significant ($p < 0.001$).

Table 3.24: ANOVA results for Coriander, Basil, and Pea Microgreen Height (cm) based on Fertilizer application, Microgreen Seeding Density, and their interaction (Fertilizer:Seeding Density).

Height (cm) Effects	Coriander P-Value	Basil P-Value	Pea P-Value
Fertilizer	< 0.001	0.35	< 0.001
Seeding Density	0.23	0.05	0.90
Fertilizer:Seeding Density	0.40	0.29	0.70

Figure 3.11 demonstrates the directionality of these results shown in Table 3.24. We can see that Basil height was unresponsive to our experimental conditions, with a barely significant response to seeding density whereby high density was associated with increased height, which is a normal response to competition. This particular response could be because of the difference in the life history compared to the larger seeds of Pea and Coriander plants; however, it could also illustrate that the standard seeding density was already high, and adding an additional 50% could make the conditions too competitive for Basil. These results can therefore be a tool to help define seeding density thresholds to optimize production. For Coriander, Fertilization had a positive significant impact on Height accumulation, independent of Seeding Density, indicating the viability of using the high seeding density for Coriander. The same relationship was seen for Pea whereby Fertilization positively influenced Height accumulation without a negative influence of Seeding Density.

Figure 3.11: Bar plot for Height (cm) for Basil (blue and purple), Cilantro (green and gray), and Pea (orange and yellow) with standard errors (+/-) and compact letter displays derived from Tukey’s HSD ($p=0.05$). Darker colors are for high density, and lighter are for standard density, with each color corresponding to a fertilization group (Yes or No).

3.2.8 Leaf Area (cm²)

Another important morphological feature of Microgreens is their leaf area, which describes the surface area of the leaves on a 2-dimensional plane (cm²). For our experiments, we took 10 leaves per Seeding Density replicate for each species except for Pea, where we took one entire plant’s leaves per Seeding Density replicate (around 12-16 leaves per plant). This was done because Basil and Coriander are more typical Microgreens which develop with an initial set of cotyledons followed by first appearance of true leaves at time of harvest; for Pea, the life history is different, as almost immediately after germination and initial growth multiple sets of leaves appear. Therefore we took as a representative of each replicate a single Pea Microgreen. These results can be seen in Figure 3.12, which shows that Basil had the lowest average Leaf Area, with Coriander having the middle, and Pea having the highest Leaf Area. Interestingly, we saw a cross-species pattern whereby fertilization resulted in higher leaf area. This was seen in every single experimental factor level. This is not surprising, given that we have shown that fertilization generally increases FW and consequently expanded leaves. Overall, Pea had around 7.4 times the leaf area of Basil, with Coriander having around 1.59 times more surface area than Basil. Furthermore, Pea had around 4.7 times the leaf area of Coriander. These results are not surprising considering the size of the Pea seeds when first sown and their life history as they develop; essentially there are far fewer seeds per cup than the other two species, so it is not surprising they exploit the available canopy space. Each Pea puts around 6 leaves out per plant at time of harvest, while both Coriander and Basil only have 2 leaves as more typical ‘true’ Microgreens. Pea Microgreens had on average 6 pairs of leaves, for a total of 12 leaves per plant. Basil had on average 2 leaves, while Cilantro also had on average 2 leaves. As Microgreens are plants that are harvested before, or right around the time of first true leaf development, it is not surprising that we had 2 leaves for the Basil and Cilantro. For Pea, the developmental process is different, but they all had around the same number of leaves, from around 12-16, depending on factors such as health or seeding density.

Figure 3.12: Bar plot for Leaf Area (cm²) for Basil (blue and purple), Cilantro (green and gray), and Pea (orange and yellow) with standard errors (+/-) and compact letter displays derived from Tukey’s HSD (p=0.05). Darker colors are for high density, and lighter are for standard density, with each color corresponding to a fertilization group (Yes or No).

3.2.9 Microgreen Health

Finally, we assessed the health of the Microgreens that we grew to identify any patterns with our experimental factors. We used a scale developed from literature cited in Deliverable 4.1: Trial protocols for microgreens production in hydroponic units (ISTIS, 2008). Figure 3.13 demonstrates some of these patterns. For instance, we can see that fertilization was associated with a higher incidence of negative health outcomes for the Basil Microgreens. However, on a scale of 1-9, we only saw minor incidences of seed or substrate corruption with average fertilized scores around 1.4. For Pea, we saw that in almost all replicates there were one or two bad seeds that had begun to become infested with fungi; this occurred slightly more often on average at high seeding density than at lower densities. For Basil, it was the substrate that was more easily affected. This could be because of the smaller stature and degree of development compared to the larger Microgreens (Coriander and Pea), which resulted in less water throughput by Basil and a more frequently wetted substrate that was not ideal for sanitation purposes. Coriander overall showed the highest resilience with no incidence of negative health outcomes at the seed, leaf, stem, or substrate level. It is not surprising to see that fertilizer can potentially result in more negative outcomes, even if the overall difference is minor considering the degree of the scale (1-9), while we classed at the highest a score of 3 only once, with frequent 2's. This is because fertilizer contains essential compounds and elements necessary for growth and development, so it is not surprising that its incidence was correlated with undesirable microbial activity, especially given the longer growing period of these Microgreens compared to Brassicaceae.

Figure 3.13: Bar plot for Microgreen Health (scale 1-9 in ascending severity) for Basil (blue and purple), Cilantro (green and gray), and Pea (orange and yellow) with standard errors (+/-) and compact letter displays derived from Tukey’s HSD (p=0.05). Darker colors are for high density, and lighter are for standard density, with each color corresponding to a fertilization group (Yes or No).

4 CONCLUSION

USAMV performed the test with the GOhydro platform in operational uncontrolled conditions, with 2 species: basil (2 varieties: Germaline Basilic Bio and Basil Grand Vert) and lettuce (3 varieties: Paris White, Little Gem and Lolla Rossa). The growing conditions of the two species of microgreens (basil and lettuce) are specific to the conditions in the operational environment, being also influenced by the external environmental conditions, for example especially by cloudiness. Having supplementary light, depending on time of year and degree of cloudiness is therefore an important consideration. By comparison with the Duncan test, we showed that the best amount of Fresh Weight is provided by Basil - Germaline Basilic Bio, with 883.40 g/m². Basil provides the highest amount of Dry Weight, with a distinctly significantly positive difference compared to the control (average). The same results after processing the data with the Duncan test, respectively the 2 varieties of basil ensure the highest Dry Weight results. The variability of the data recorded for total phenols is very high, and the statistical processing does not highlight results with a significant difference. Lettuce contains 98-105 mg/kg, and basil 106-127 mg/kg total phenols. From the morphological analysis of plant development, both in basil and in lettuce, no disease attack is registered, due to the maintenance of the health of the water in the feed basin and a quantity of around 6.4-6.5 mg L⁻¹ of dissolved oxygen. An exception is made in the case of lettuce, the Paris White variety, which registered a grade 4 in the degree of attack until harvest. Due to the higher thermal oscillations than in the case of the experiment under controlled conditions, the degree of attack was slightly higher. This is due exclusively to this variety in which the seed had an inadequate quality for the production of hydroponic microgreens. The conclusions of the experiment, which require the optimization of production procedures with the GOhydro platform, are related to the type of substrate used, the density of the microgreens culture, the attack by pathogens and the seed germination procedure.

In Denmark, we varied two experimental factors (Seeding Density and Fertilization) for our three species (Basil, Pea, and Coriander) to better understand ways to optimize production. We identified some key tradeoffs, such as the increase in Fresh Weight accumulation and the decrease in Dry Weight accumulation via fertilization. However, fertilization was also associated with increased Height and Leaf Area. Finally, we also showed that there was a slight negative effect of fertilization on Microgreen Health. Overall, we have shown that, despite tradeoffs, it is likely that fertilization is a highly net-positive input for producing Microgreens. The primary auxiliary concern, identified in Deliverable 1.2, is the need to control pH to ensure optimal nutrient uptake from the fertilization solution. Using the GOhydro sensor kit offers a key tool to inform the user when they need to add in a buffer. Concerning our second experimental factor, Seeding Density, we identified that it was space efficient, but it did not scale up entirely linearly and produce 50% more biomass, even though it was sown with 50% more seed weight. There was therefore a slight inefficiency in output, but this was compensated for by increased space efficiency. Therefore, if space is not limiting, we recommend a standard or lower seeding density; if space is limiting, we recommend a high seeding density.

Overall, considering the two separate, but related, sets of results obtained from our two different Microgreen production pilot sites in Denmark and Romania, we have shown some important Microgreen production dynamics. Firstly, we have shown the operational capacity of the GOhydro sensor kit, as we were able to successfully send real-time data from our pilot sites back to Greece. This information can be integrated with the production data we have obtained to begin to understand the relationship between production and environmental information to inform the average user about production activities. Secondly, we have elaborated on some important considerations in uncontrolled operational environments that can generally approximate the growing conditions of the average targeted user, such as offices or homes. In Romania, we had a low-cost hydroponic system built of easily accessible and affordable PVC, pump, and LED light system. In Denmark, we had an even simpler setup that had only automation of the lights and temperature, which are realistic controlled parameters in most homes or offices. We simply used a table with a tray on top of it which housed our Microgreens; within this tray each Microgreen was sown in a cup with holes in the bottom to allow adequate drainage, an essential consideration, to avoid anaerobic conditions. Our results found that Microgreens can easily be grown in these uncontrolled conditions with a few important considerations: that environmental parameters be held within a range (discussed in section 2.2.3 and 3.1) and that a light source be utilized, either directly via LED or HPS, or indirectly via incident sunlight depending on the time of year. In Romania, they used incident sunlight coming from a window as their light source; in the higher Danish latitude,

we used a supplementary light (HPS) to achieve the necessary requisite DLI to ensure optimal growth. It is worth mentioning, although we did not directly test this, that Microgreens can be grown in the dark (see examples in our literature review in Deliverable 1.1), but the quality—such as coloration—and quantity will be affected. The use of light, and what type of light, is therefore context-dependent according to the needs of the user. Finally, both Romanian and Danish pilot sites identified the large amount of species-specific variation; therefore, the selection of Microgreens to grow is an important first step for optimizing and parameterizing the growth environment. Oftentimes, there are very specific species-related contexts or pathways that necessitate nuanced analyses. Therefore, overall, we have identified key production tradeoffs and pathways for Microgreen production that can be used by a variety of actors that are applicable to a variety of Microgreen species. These results have elucidated some essential results that can inform optimal Microgreen production while highlighting that there is no single ‘best case’ scenario, but in fact there are tradeoffs that require tailoring the production environment to the user’s needs. We have shown examples of this in highly controlled environments (Deliverable 1.2), semi-controlled environments (Deliverable 4.2), and uncontrolled environments (Deliverable 4.3) to offer a range of informative material that can be used by interested Microgreen growers of any skill or experience level. We have offered step-by-step instructions and showcased different potential environmental and production setups that can be used, and their associated productive outputs. In conclusion, we have shown that Microgreens are generally robust and require a generally forgiving range of environmental conditions that pair well with uncontrolled human inhabited environments, such as offices or homes. We found that there were not huge differences in productive capacity in highly controlled environments compared to uncontrolled ones. Therefore, using these deliverables as the beginning stages of a database that can be integrated into the GOhydro platform can offer valuable information to interested Microgreen growers of any educational or experience level.

5 REFERENCES

1. Moraru, P.I.; Rusu, T.; Mintas, O.S. Trial Protocol for Evaluating Platforms for Growing Microgreens in Hydroponic Conditions. *Foods* 2022, 11, 1327. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods11091327>
2. <https://www.meteoromania.ro/grafice> (accessed 12/12/2022 and 03/01/2023)
3. Tavan, M.; Wee, B.; Brodie, G.; Fuentes, S.; Pang, A.; Gupta, D. Optimizing Sensor-Based Irrigation Management in a Soilless Vertical Farm for Growing Microgreens. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* 2021, 4, 622720. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2020.622720>
4. ISTIS, 2008. Metodologia examinării valorii agronomice și de utilizare (Testul VAU). Institutul de Stat pentru Testarea și Înregistrarea Soiurilor, p. 26. <http://istis.ro/image/data/download/publicatii/MetodicaVAU.pdf>